

Novel one pot synthesis of ethylphenidate hydrochloride with significantly high yield and purity

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In the present work we have reported an industrially feasible and economically viable novel one pot process for synthesis of ethylphenidate hydrochloride with significantly high yields and purity.

Keywords: Green chemistry, genotoxic impurities consideration.

Introduction

Ethylphenidate (EPH) is a psychostimulant and a close analog of methylphenidate. Ethylphenidate acts as both a dopamine reuptake inhibitor and norepinephrine reuptake inhibitor, meaning it effectively boosts the levels of the norepinephrine and dopamine neurotransmitters in the brain, by binding to, and partially blocking the transporter proteins that normally remove those monoamines from the synaptic cleft¹.

Ethylphenidate metabolizes into methylphenidate and ritalinic acid². Tiny amounts of ethylphenidate can be formed *in vivo* when ethanol and methylphenidate are coingested, via hepatic transesterification³. Ethylphenidate formation appears to be more common when large quantities of methylphenidate and alcohol are consumed at the same time, such as in non-medical use or overdose scenarios⁴. However, the transesterification process of methylphenidate to ethylphenidate, as tested in mice liver, was dominant in the inactive (–)-enantiomer but showed a prolonged and increased maximal plasma concentration of the active (+)-enantiomer of methylphenidate⁵.

Synthetic methods for preparing ethyl- α -phenyl- α -(2-piperidyl) acetate for the preparation of ethylphenidate are reported in using a sequence involving the resolution of the amide derivative of the corresponding erythro isomer, conversion to the threo isomer, followed by the hydrolysis of the

amide to the corresponding acid in isolated form, and esterification of the resulting acid with methanol to give methylphenidate^{6–12} and hydrolysis of methylphenidate give its acid derivative, it is reacted with ethanol and hydrochloric acid give ethylphenidate¹³.

The available methods make use of drastic reaction conditions, more unit operations; additional purification by chromatography to get high enantiomeric (threo and erythro) and chemical purity which leads to loss of yield and which is not desirable for commercial manufacturing as well as plant-scale point of view.

Moreover, these processes involves tedious reaction conditions, loss of yield, long reaction time cycle, more energy consumption, loss of human hours and involvement of more inventories as well as unit operations.

In view of above, we have developed an improved process that addresses the problems associated with the processes reported in the prior art. The present process does not involve more unit operations. Further, the process does not require critical workup procedure. Accordingly, the present paper provides a simple process for the preparation of ethylphenidate hydrochloride, which is efficient, cost effective, in reaction itself by designing optimum condition for reaction to reduce effluent load, environment friendly and commercially scalable for large scale operations.

Scheme 1. One pot route of synthesis of ethylphenidate hydrochloride.

Experimental

Materials and reagent:

Threo-2-phenyl-2-(piperidin-2-yl) acetamide, ethanol, sulphuric acid, isopropanol, isopropanolic hydrochloric acid, activated charcoal and *n*-butanol.

Preparation of ethylphenidate hydrochloride from threo-2-phenyl-2-piperidyl acetamide:

In ethanol (500 ml), threo-2-phenyl-2-(piperidine-2-yl) acetamide (100 g, 1.0 mole) was added at ambient temperature. The reaction mixture was cooled to 2–8°C followed by drop wise addition of sulfuric acid (224.4 g, 5.0 mole) over 30–40 min. The solid mass obtained was stirred for 15–20 min at 5–10°C and temperature was then raised up to room temperature. The reaction mass was further heated at temperature 80 to 95°C for 15–30 min and maintained at reflux for 30 h to distil some volume of ethanol followed by adding fresh ethanol into the reaction mass. Further it is maintained at reflux for 5 h. After completion of reaction, ethanol was distilled off and degassed under vacuum. The thick residue was cooled to 20–25°C and water (1000 ml) was added. Cooled the mass up at 10–15°C and stirred for 10 min followed by adjusting its pH at 6–8 by adding caustic soda. Into a reaction mixture, dichloromethane (200 ml) was added at 25–30°C and pH was adjusted to 11.0–12.5. The mixture

was then stirred for 30 min at 25–30°C. The organic layer was separated. Again dichloromethane (75 ml x2) was added to aqueous layer and separated. Dichloromethane was distilled out at temperature 45–50°C and degassed under vacuum. After completion of distillation, isopropanol (800 ml) added into the oily mass followed by charcoal treatment. The reaction mixture was filtered and washed with isopropanol (50 ml). The filtrate was then cooled up to 5–10°C. Isopropanolic hydrochloric acid (80 g, 1.1 mole) was added to the reaction mass followed by stirring for 30 min at 5–10°C. The reaction mixture was heated at 55–65°C for 5–10 min followed by cooling at 0–5°C. The reaction mass was maintained at 0–8°C for 30 min. Filtered the mass at 0–8°C and washed with isopropanol (50 ml). The wet cake was dried at 40–45°C under vacuum to get ethylphenidate hydrochloride (92.0 g, 81.5%) having HPLC purity: Threo content: 99.9%, Erythro content: 0.10%.

Preparation of ethylphenidate hydrochloride from threo-2-phenyl-2-piperidyl acetamide [Threo isomer NLT 85%]:

In ethanol (500 ml), threo-2-phenyl-2-(piperidin-2-yl) acetamide (100 g, 1.0 mole) was added at ambient temperature. The reaction mixture was cooled to 2–8°C followed by addition of sulphuric acid (224.4 g, 5.0 mole) drop wise within 30–40 min. The mass was stirred for 15–20 min at 5–10°C

and temperature was then raised up to room temperature. The reaction mass was heated at temperature 80 to 95°C within 15–30 min and maintained at reflux for 30 h to distil off volume of ethanol followed by adding fresh ethanol into the reaction mass. Further, it was refluxed for 5 h. After completion of reaction, ethanol was distilled out at 85–95°C and degassed under vacuum. The thick residue was cooled to 20–25°C and water (1000 ml) was added. Cooled the mass up to 10–15°C and stirred for 10 min followed by adjusting pH at 6–8 by adding caustic soda. Into the reaction mixture dichloro-methane (200 ml) was added at 25–30°C and pH was adjusted to 11.0–12.5. The mixture was then stirred for 30 min at 25–30°C. The organic layer was separated out. Again dichloromethane (75 ml x2) was added to aqueous layer and separated. Combined both organic layers. Dichloromethane is distilled off at temperature 45–50°C and degassed under vacuum. After completion of distillation, isopropanol (300 ml) added into the oily mass followed by charcoal treatment. The reaction mixture was filtered and washed with isopropanol (50 ml). The filtrate was then cooled up to 5–10°C. Isopropanolic hydrochloric acid (80 g, 1.1 mole) was added to the reaction mass followed by stirring for 30 min at 5–10°C. The reaction mixture was heated at 55–65°C for 5–10 min followed by cooling at 0–5°C. The reaction mass was maintained at 0–8°C for 30 min. Filtered the mass at 0–8°C and washed with isopropanol (50 ml). The wet cake was dried at 40–45°C under vacuum to get ethylphenidate hydrochloride (92.0 g, 81.5%) having HPLC purity: Threo content: 99.10%. Erythro content: 0.90%.

Purification of crude ethylphenidate hydrochloride:

Crude ethylphenidate hydrochloride (90 g) was added into the *n*-butanol (540 ml) at temperature 25–30°C. The reaction mass was heated up to 110–120°C and maintained for 10–15 min. The mass was then cooled to 25–30°C within 2–3 h and maintained for 30 min followed by filtration at 25–30°C. The obtained cake was washed with *n*-butanol (90 ml) and dried at 75–80°C under vacuum to get pure 168 g ethylphenidate hydrochloride having HPLC purity: Threo content: 99.95%, Erythro content: 0.05%.

Results and discussion

The preferred embodiment of the present invention is to provide a novel *in situ* process for preparation of ethylphenidate hydrochloride. The esterification can be per-

formed by reacting formula II with ethanol in the presence of catalyst.

As per the observations of researchers of the present work is that the use of 9–10 volumes of the solvent gives higher quality as compared to use of 2–3 volumes of solvent at particular stage. The difference is broadly described as shown in Table 1.

Table 1		
	Crude	Pure
Solvent	isopropanol	isopropanol
Solvent volume	9–10	2–3
HPLC purity	~99.9%	~99.1%

The volumes of solvent of methanol, ethanol, *n*-propanol, isopropanol, *n*-butanol, isobutanol, tert-butanol or acetone and mixture thereof, added into oily mass of ethylphenidate free base, are preferably 2–3 volumes.

In other words, after distillation of the solvent such as dichloromethane, ethylacetate, diethyl ether, diisopropylether, methylethylether, toluene or xylene or mixture thereof, the obtained oily mass of ethylphenidate free base is treated with different solvent volumes and gives different purity results as described in Table 1. Hence crude product may need purification to remove unwanted isomer and impurities.

Ethylphenidate hydrochloride of formula I is purified by treating with suitable solvent. The suitable solvents include methanol, ethanol, isopropanol, *n*-butanol, isobutanol, tert-butanol, acetone, acetonitrile or mixture thereof. The reaction temperature is ambient to reflux temperature, preferably up to 60–120°C for a time sufficient. The reaction mixture is then cooled to 0–30°C, preferably 25–30°C and maintained for 30 min followed by filtration at 25–30°C. The obtained cake is washed with solvent, dried and gives yield more than 99.9% ethylphenidate hydrochloride.

Hence, optimized parameters for the purification in present work make the product pharmacopoeially acceptable worldwide.

Final molecule characterised by ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, FTIR, CHNO and Mass analysis:

¹H NMR:

The proton magnetic resonance spectrum (¹H NMR spectrum) of ethylphenidate hydrochloride in CDCl₃ was recorded at 400.13 MHz instrument which exhibits the followings sig-

Table 2

Sr. No.	ppm (H)	Type of signal	Number of protons	Type of proton
1.	1.35	Triplet	3H	Protons of -CH ₃ group attached on -CH ₂ of ester
2.	3.67	Multiplet	2H	Protons of -CH ₂ group of -OCH ₃ of ester
3.	1.80	Quarterate	2H	Protons of -CH ₂ group of cyclic ring of piperidine
4.	2.89	Multiplet	1H	1 Carbons of -CH group between of cyclic ring of piperidine and benzene
5.	2.0 to 4.34	Multiplet	7H	Protons of -CH ₂ group of cyclic ring of piperidine
6.	8.94	Broad singlet	1H	Protons of -NH group of cyclic ring of piperidine
7.	7.28 to 7.37	Multiplet	5H	Protons of aromatic ring
8.	10.27	Broad singlet	1H	Protons of HCl group

Fig. 1

nals in the ppm scale described Table 2 and Fig. 1.

¹³C NMR:

The ¹³C NMR spectrum of ethylphenidate hydrochloride in CDCl₃ was taken at 100.13 MHz which shows following signals in the ppm scale described Table 3 and Fig. 2.

FTIR:

IR of spectrum of ethylphenidate hydrochloride was recorded in KBr pellet in the range 400–4000 cm⁻¹. Assignments for the characteristics bands in the infra-red spectrum confirmed the formation of compound and given in Table 4

Fig. 2

Table 3

Sr. No.	ppm	Type of carbon
1.	13.85	1 Carbon of -CH ₃ group attached on -CH ₂ of ester
2.	21.91	1 Carbons of -CH ₂ group of cyclic ring of piperidine
3.	22.53 to 58.92	4 Carbons of -CH ₂ group of cyclic ring of piperidine
4.	54.10	1 Carbons of -CH group between cyclic ring of piperidine and benzene
5.	62.34	1 Carbon of -CH ₂ group of -CH ₃ of ester
6.	76.76 to 134.25	6 Carbons of aromatic ring
7.	171.40	1 Carbons of -C=O carbonyl group

and Fig. S1 (Supplementary).

CHN analysis:

CHN and O analysis of ethylphenidate hydrochloride confirmed the formation of compound and given in Table 5.

Table 4

Sr. No.	Band at frequency (cm ⁻¹)	Due to stretching of
1.	3133 to 2864	Aromatic -C-H stretching
2.	1719	Carbonyl group of ester
3.	2650 to 2606	Piperidine ring -C-H stretching
4.	1577	Aromatic -C=C- stretching
5.	1171	Ester group -C-O stretching

Table 5

Sr. No.	Element	Theoretical value (%)	Observed values (%)	Observed value
1.	C	63.48	63.69	Matches with theoretical value
2.	N	4.94	4.89	Matches with theoretical value
3.	H	7.81	7.71	Matches with theoretical value
4.	O	11.28	11.16	Matches with theoretical value

Mass analysis:

Mass analysis of ethylphenidate hydrochloride confirmed the formation of compound and given in Fig. S2 (Supplementary). Base peak on 247 m/e.

Conclusion

The synthesis of ethylphenidate hydrochloride and its structural confirmation was made by spectroscopic and analytical data i.e. spectra, mass, proton NMR and carbon-13 NMR, CHN analysis, ROS also support formation of the product¹⁴.

The above results are complying the formation of product by applying one pot synthesis in one step instead of three steps and best achievement of green chemistry, route. We have avoid the use of hazardous chemicals, number of solvents, catalyst and reagents. This process is commercially highly effective as it save man powder, time, utility, health and safety of man; it's frankly for environment because we have reduced bulk waste generation and same is the basic principal of green chemistry.

One more important benefit of this process is genotoxic impurity causing cancer (Cancer; "something wrong with the genes"...), we have avoided more toxic and carcinogenic chemical (thionyl chloride, phosphorus trichloride, phosphorus pentachloride, phosphorus oxychloride and many more like those are using for acylation of acid to acid chloride) and intermediate (acid chloride intermediate) those are responsible for cancer.

Limits of genotoxic impurities are very low in active pharmaceutical ingredients (API) and these are less than 50 ppm in finish good (API) same achieving is too much critical with losses of yield, energy, coast as well as identification is too much difficult in API.

So many factors are responsible for making a product free from hazardous waste and impurities as per guideline of ICH. In this process we have considered all the parameter

like environment, health and safety, economical viable and too much beneficial for nation.

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